

Analysis of Cape Jason and the Church Visitor Experiences Based on TripAdvisor Reviews

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Abstract

International travelers extensively use the internet to plan trips and read other travelers' reviews. The aim of this research is to analyze the visitor experiences of Cape Jason and the Church are located in the Perşembe district of Ordu province on the Black Sea coast of Türkiye, as a tourist attraction associated with the recognition of the destination and the development of its destination identity. For this purpose, online reviews from TripAdvisor were examined and analyzed using the netnography method. The findings revealed the main themes of "positive comments", "information", "negative comments", "advice", and "warning", along with 53 subthemes. "Positive comments" emerged as the most frequent main theme, with "landscape" being the most prominent subtheme, indicating the strong role of natural beauty and environmental aesthetics in shaping the visitor experiences. However, themes such as "guidance" and "need for content" suggest that visitors seek not only spatial experiences but also

historical and cultural context. Although negative comments were fewer, they highlighted issues related to infrastructure and maintenance. The study contributes to the tourism experience literature by providing a context-specific and theory-driven interpretation of visitor experiences in a relatively underexplored heritage setting. By linking the findings to the dimensions of memorable tourism experience (MTE), it demonstrates that online reviews reflect interconnected hedonic, cognitive, and behavioral components of tourism experiences. Future research may examine how MTE dimensions vary across visitor segments and cultural contexts to better understand the formation of memorable experiences in heritage destinations.

Keywords: Visitor Experiences, TripAdvisor, Cape Jason and the Church, Perşembe.

JEL Codes: Z30, Z31, D12

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1. Introduction

Understanding how tourist experiences are interpreted and translated into satisfaction has become a critical issue in contemporary tourism research (Juliana et al., 2024). As destinations increasingly compete through the experiences they offer, a key challenge lies in ensuring that these experiences are perceived positively and transformed into satisfaction, loyalty, and revisit intentions. In this context, destination success depends not only on attracting new visitors but also on sustaining demand by effectively managing tourists' experiential evaluations. Satisfaction, as an outcome of these evaluations, plays a central role in encouraging repeat visits and positive word-of-mouth, while also contributing to the economic sustainability and competitive advantage of destinations by reducing marketing costs and price sensitivity (Jarvis et al., 2016; Cosvi et al., 2019). Providing positive and satisfying experiences is therefore essential not only for fostering revisit intentions and customer loyalty (Cavlak & Cop, 2019), but also for enhancing destination reputation and perceived image in an environment where experiences are widely shared (Awaloedin et al., 2024). In addition, destinations that take into account tourists' feedback and continuously improve their facilities can both directly strengthen revisit intentions and indirectly attract new visitors through the influence of online reviews (Oğuz & Timur, 2020). Within this framework, tourist satisfaction can be understood as a multidimensional evaluation shaped by factors such as service quality, facility standards, price fairness, and safety, highlighting the responsibility of destinations to design memorable and distinctive experiences that support long-term behavioral outcomes (Öktem & Akdu, 2022). Therefore, tourism should be conceptualized not merely as a service-based sector, but as a system shaped by how tourists interpret and evaluate their experiences.

Nowadays, digital technologies and social media play an extremely important role for tourism businesses to improve their product and service quality. The opportunities and environments created by digital technologies are seen as a new interaction channel that facilitates businesses to communicate with customers and customers to communicate with each other (Nilashi et al., 2018). It is noteworthy that tourists use online reviews to reduce perceived risk and uncertainty towards tourism-based activities and destinations (Su et al., 2022). International travelers extensively use the Internet to plan their trips and read reviews from other travelers (Liu & Park, 2015). According to the Travel Industry Association of America, 64% of travelers plan their trips based on search engines and social media reviews. While until recently, tourists were more likely to share their experiences with their personal reference circles, online travel experience platforms have changed this. Today, people have started to refer to reviews of pe-

ople and organizations that they consider important on online platforms, along with their close circles. The focal point of using a netnography design in this study is the increasing influence of online platforms on perceptions and decision-making processes related to touristic experiences. TripAdvisor, the world's largest tourism and travel-oriented user review platform, is an important reference source that provides an online environment for tourists to share their opinions on various aspects of destinations and hotels (Nilashi et al., 2018). Online reviews on TripAdvisor, as a form of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), represent user-generated content through which visitor experiences are articulated and shared. These eWOM contents provide rich insights into visitor experiences, which can be interpreted within the framework of memorable tourism experience (MTE).

A growing body of research has utilized TripAdvisor reviews as a data source to explore different dimensions of tourism experiences and visitor perceptions. For example, Atasoy (2025) examines cultural heritage experiences in the ancient city of Olympos through tourist narratives and reveals that visitor experiences are shaped by the interaction of historical, natural, and emotional elements, reflecting cognitive, sensory, and affective responses. Similarly, Akgül (2025) focuses on sacred heritage sites and analyzes how visitors construct their experiences in religious contexts, highlighting the role of cultural meaning and spiritual perception. In a different context, Can (2025) explores the digital representation of gastronomic identity through TripAdvisor reviews, demonstrating how user-generated content contributes to the formation of destination image and culinary perception. Çifçi and Kızılırmak (2025), on the other hand, examine customer experience components in vegan restaurants using a netnographic approach, emphasizing experiential dimensions related to service, product, and lifestyle preferences.

In the context of heritage and museum studies, Islam (2025) analyzes visitor sentiments in archaeological sites, revealing how emotional expressions in online reviews reflect satisfaction and perceived value, while Ferguson and Walby (2025) investigate military museums and highlight how visitors interpret authenticity and engagement within historical narratives. Similarly, Plichta and Pecela (2025) focus on religious heritage in Vilnius and examine how tourists perceive and evaluate sacred spaces through online narratives. Samida (2025) approaches the topic from a different perspective by analyzing digital memory and dark heritage, showing how visitors interpret controversial historical sites through emotionally and culturally loaded narratives.

Beyond single-destination or thematic studies, some research adopts more advanced analytical approaches. For instance, Candrea et al. (2025) employ sentiment analysis and topic modeling techniques to identify visitor experience patterns and differen-

ces across visitor segments in mountain museums, providing a cross-country comparative perspective. Similarly, Sidor et al. (2025) analyze geoheritage destinations using online data to identify aggregated experience dimensions and their implications for destination management organizations, while Tanrıverdi et al. (2025) examine cave tourism experiences through content analysis and reveal the key experiential dimensions shaping visitor perceptions. Finally, Tuncer (2025) investigates shopping center preferences based on online reviews, demonstrating how consumer decision-making processes are influenced by perceived service quality, environment, and experiential factors.

Overall, these studies demonstrate that TripAdvisor reviews provide rich insights into tourists' emotional responses, experiential evaluations, and perception of destination attributes. However, despite this growing body of literature, existing studies have largely focused on specific contexts or themes and have often remained descriptive, highlighting the need for more context-specific and theory-driven research that integrates experiential dimensions within a comprehensive analytical framework.

Cape Jason and its Church located in the Perşembe district of Ordu province on the Black Sea coast of Türkiye. Cape Jason and its Church represent a distinctive cultural heritage setting that combines archaeological significance with natural landscape features, thereby offering a multifaceted touristic experience. Existing studies in the tourism literature have increasingly utilized online reviews to examine visitor perceptions across various destinations; however, these studies have largely focused on more well-known destinations and have generally remained at a descriptive level.

In this context, there is a need for studies that provide a more in-depth understanding of how tourist experiences are perceived and expressed, particularly in relatively underexplored heritage settings. Accordingly, this study aims to examine how visitor experiences are constructed and interpreted through user-generated content and to reveal the experiential dimensions reflected in online narratives. From this perspective, Cape Jason Church is used as an empirical case to better understand how meaning-making processes, emotional responses, and contextual factors shape tourist experiences. In doing so, the study is expected to contribute to the tourism experience literature by providing context-specific insights and by offering a more comprehensive interpretation of visitor experiences based on naturally occurring data.

Although online reviews have become a widely used data source for understanding tourist experiences, much of the existing research has primarily focused on identifying surface-level themes such as satisfaction, complaints, or destination attributes. While

these descriptive insights are valuable, they often remain limited in explaining how these experiences are cognitively processed, emotionally internalized, and later transformed into memorable outcomes. In particular, there is a lack of studies that reinterpret user-generated content through a theoretically grounded experiential perspective. Memorable tourism experience (MTE) theory suggests that tourism experiences are multidimensional, shaped by interconnected emotional, cognitive, and behavioral components (Kim et al., 2012). However, the integration of this theoretical perspective into netnography-based analyses of online reviews remains limited.

In this context, the present study moves beyond descriptive categorization by reinterpreting online visitor reviews within a multidimensional experiential framework. By linking naturally occurring user-generated content with the theoretical dimensions of MTE, the study provides a deeper understanding of how tourist experiences are constructed, interpreted, and transformed into meaningful and memorable experiences in a relatively underexplored heritage destination. Therefore, the originality of this study lies not only in its empirical context but also in its ability to bridge netnographic data with experience-based tourism theory. Accordingly, in order to operationalize the research aim and provide a structured analytical framework, the study is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1: What are the main themes reflected in visitors' online reviews of Cape Jason and the Church?

RQ2: How can these themes be interpreted in relation to the dimensions of memorable tourism experience (MTE)?

RQ3: What factors contribute to positive and negative visitor evaluations in the context of the destination?

RQ4: How do visitors' online reviews reflect post-visit engagement such as recommendations and advice?

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Importance of Online Visitor Reviews for Destinations

The scope of tourist experiences and the sharing of these experiences are important issues for destinations seeking to remain competitive in the tourism sector (Decrop & Snelders, 2005). In addition, feedback regarding tourist experiences provides destinations with the opportunity to strengthen their tourism product design and improve the overall tourist experience. With the widespread use of digital technologies today, the sharing of tourist experiences has accelerated, and the impact it creates has become significantly stronger (Sultan et al., 2019). With the advancements in technology, it is seen that the social media phenomenon, which includes various

websites and online platforms where people share all kinds of experiences in different ways, has developed (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010). In recent years, online sharing sites where consumers share their past experiences have become valuable sources of information that allow consumers to access important, detailed and reliable information that they research before choosing a product (Liu & Park, 2015). It is noteworthy that online platforms are increasingly preferred by consumers to help them plan their trips and make informed decisions about tourism-related products. This has become especially important during and after the Covid-19 pandemic, when tourists do not want to experience unexpected events and seek information from sites perceived as accurate and unbiased. Online review readers prefer to seek personal recommendations from other tourists to mitigate potential risks associated with a destination and avoid making poor choices (Su et al., 2022). The development of new online information sources created by users by sharing experiences before, during and after the vacation has become an important issue to be emphasized in terms of influencing the purchase decision process of tourists (Kladou & Mavragani, 2015). Because it has been found that social media content is more reliable in terms of tourists' perceptions than advertisements on official tourism websites or mass media (Kladou & Mavragani, 2015).

There are many online travel review platforms serve as important channels through which tourists share their experiences, thereby shaping the perceptions and decisions of potential visitors. In recent years, many online review platforms in the tourism sector, such as TripAdvisor, Lonely Planet, and Google Maps, have become more prevalent in research and practice, expanding the use of new analytical technologies (Taecharungroj & Mathayomchan, 2019). The most popular of these platforms is TripAdvisor, an online social travel review platform created by its users and a website application for searching for travel-related prices. TripAdvisor users review their travel experiences and supplement them with photos, allowing potential tourists to research tourist attractions and accommodations. As of 2024, TripAdvisor is among the world's most preferred online travel platforms, with over 455 million monthly active users and over 290 million reviews across 49 markets, searchable in 28 languages (TripAdvisor, 2024). Depth of perception is achieved by gathering information from as many sources as possible. Individuals tend to gather as much information as possible before making a purchase from places like destinations, hotels, and restaurants (Kladou & Mavragani, 2015). TripAdvisor is a social network based on the idea that tourists rely on the reviews of other tourists to plan their trips and can get satisfactory help from them in their decisions. Most of the information processed is independently created by its users. Reviews and ratings are posted here about a destination,

accommodation establishment, attraction, tourist supply attraction or any other tourism-related element, good or service. This online platform is also designed to save time in terms of finding people who share similar travel tastes (Miguens et al., 2008).

The TripAdvisor platform is one of the sources of information that can be used to analyze tourist satisfaction with a tourist destination. The information obtained from this platform begins to take shape based on the preferences, experiences, and evaluations of tourists visiting the destination, and emerges as a new combination that may also include the opinions of those who live in the destination, visit the destination, have experience in similar destinations, or simply comment based on the comments of users on this platform. This combination of this information does not exhibit any permanent characteristics. It has a structure that can change rapidly with new interpretations of events. This structure keeps the platform's users constantly active in terms of destination-related information. Tourist reviews and recommendations can be a decisive factor in influencing potential tourists' decisions to visit or avoid certain destinations. Thanks to mobile applications, users can plan their vacations, compare the lowest prices for hotels, airlines, and cruise ships, and make reservations (Awaloedin et al., 2024; TripAdvisor, 2024). TripAdvisor is a platform that works to gain a deeper understanding of how tourism businesses and tourists are changing the online tourism market in a particular destination. The changes brought about by TripAdvisor and similar social networks have led to a new form of competition (Miguens et al., 2008). TripAdvisor is visited by approximately 463 million people every month. The platform assists individuals in making vacation decisions and enables them to share their post-vacation experiences with other users. When examining the volume of these shares, it is evident that there are over 859 million reviews on the platform (TripAdvisor, 2024).

Interpreting and analyzing the visitor experience in tourism is an important tool for revealing tourists' purchasing behaviors, perceptions, and preference patterns regarding products and services during their travel process. The relationship between online reviews and tourists' purchasing decisions is important data that should be taken into consideration in destination management and marketing. Optimizing service and product quality by taking visitor reviews into account will directly affect customer satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, analyzing visitor reviews provides fundamental data that guides the improvement of marketing strategies, increases the tourism appeal of the destination, and ultimately promotes a sustainable and competitive tourism environment. By analyzing visitor reviews (emotions), decision-makers identify critical areas of satisfaction and areas that need improvement, enabling them to develop strategies to more effectively meet visitor

expectations. These initiatives encourage long-term engagement and positive word-of-mouth communication necessary for the growth of sustainable tourism. As a result, adopting a more responsive and adaptable approach to destination management by considering the results of visitor review analyses will lead to more lasting success, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty (Singgalen, 2024). Based on this, data from social media platforms will provide destination management with significant opportunities to understand visitor trends and expectations. In this context, the current research aims to reveal the details of the experiences of Cape Jason and the Church based on the TripAdvisor comments and develops recommendations for destination management based on research results.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of this study is grounded in the experience-based approach to tourism and consumer behavior theories, which emphasize that tourists' perceptions, emotions, and evaluations formed during and after the travel experience play a decisive role in satisfaction, loyalty, and behavioral intentions. In tourism research, experience has been conceptualized as a critical determinant of post-visit behaviors and decision-making processes, as tourists rely on past experiences to form expectations and recommendations for others (Meenakshy et al., 2024). In this context, online visitor reviews are considered a reflection of tourists' experiential evaluations and emotional responses, consistent with the principles of experiential marketing and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) theory. eWOM theory suggests that user-generated content on digital platforms significantly influences tourists' decision-making processes, destination image formation, and future behavioral intentions (Huete-Alcocer, 2017). By analyzing visitor emotions and experiences expressed in online reviews, the study adopts an experience-centered and eWOM-based theoretical perspective to understand how service quality, destination attributes, and perceived value shape visitor satisfaction and loyalty. Accordingly, the analysis of TripAdvisor reviews is theoretically justified as a valid and reliable means of capturing tourists' experiential perceptions and translating them into actionable insights for destination management.

In addition to this perspective, the concept of memorable tourism experience (MTE) further strengthens the theoretical foundation of the study by providing a multidimensional understanding of how tourism experiences are internalized and remembered by visitors. MTE theory conceptualizes tourism experiences as consisting of emotional, cognitive, and experiential components that contribute to long-term memory formation (Kim et al., 2012). These dimensions play a significant role in shaping sa-

tisfaction, behavioral intentions, and post-visit evaluations. In this context, online visitor reviews can be considered as reflections of memorable aspects of the tourism experience, as they capture the elements that visitors find most meaningful and worth sharing.

In line with this theoretical perspective, although no study in the existing literature has examined the same tourist attraction using the same methodological framework as the present research, several empirical studies have employed online visitor reviews and similar analytical approaches, thereby providing a valuable conceptual and methodological background. Altınay Özdemir and Topaloğlu (2023) analyzed 638 user reviews of the ancient city of Knidos and identified key themes such as attraction, place perception, sustainability concerns, attachment, and behavioral intention. Similarly, Öztürk and Akay (2024) examined TripAdvisor reviews of 22 "cittaslow" cities in Turkey and revealed core dimensions of tourist experience, including hedonism, innovation, renewal, participation, local culture, meaningfulness and knowledge acquisition. These studies demonstrate the applicability of experience-based and eWOM perspectives in interpreting tourists' online evaluations.

Studies focusing on the regional context further support the relevance of this approach. Bahtiyar Karadeniz et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of regional cooperation between decision makers, tourism operators and local people in the protection, management and promotion issues in their studies examining the natural tourist supply resources of Ordu province. Yiğit & Aktaş (2025) revealed how visitors perceive the touristic experiences of Deyrulzafaran Monastery through a netnographic approach. Specifically addressing Cape Jason and the Church, Kara et al. (2022) evaluated the area from a sustainable cultural tourism perspective and underlined the need to balance conservation and utilization while enhancing promotional and marketing activities. Korkut et al. (2023), using data from social media platforms, found that the touristic attractiveness of the Cape Jason and the Church recreation area stems from the integration of historical elements with natural landscape features.

Building on this theoretical and empirical background, the primary objective of this study is to investigate online reviews of Cape Jason and the Church, to draw inferences about visitor experiences, and to develop recommendations for destination management based on these inferences. In this context, online reviews from TripAdvisor, a travel review platform that facilitates travel planning, were examined and analyzed. This theoretical framework guides the analysis of online reviews by enabling the identification of prominent experiential themes related to Cape Jason and the Church, which serve

as a basis for developing destination management recommendations. Comments on Cape Jason and the Church were analyzed through netnographic analysis, identifying the focal points of tourist attraction experiences. The findings will provide a clearer understanding of experiences related to Cape Jason and the Church and increase opportunities for improvement.

2.3. Cape Jason and the Church

Cape Jason, the only peninsula with a church on the Black Sea coast (Ordu Provincial Directorate of Culture

and Tourism, 2024), is located on the coastal road within the Çaytepe neighborhood of the Perşembe district of Ordu province (between Fatsa Bolaman and Perşembe Efirli Beach). A review of relevant literature reveals that the area has been inhabited since ancient times, and that the church was built by the local Greeks in 1868 and restored in 2004 (Okuyucu, 2013; Buyruk, 2019; Meral & Kumargal, 2020). Cape Jason is currently protected as a first-degree archaeological site and a second-degree natural site (Ordu Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2024). Photograph 1 presents different views of Cape Jason and the Church.

Photo 1. Photos of Cape Jason and the Church

Source: <https://ordu.ktb.gov.tr/tr-130751/yason-burnu-persembeordu.html>, <https://karadeniz.gov.tr/yason-kilisesi/>, Buyruk, 2019

Cape Jason and the Church are visited as part of cultural tourism, while also being a destination of choice for those who want to watch and photograph the sunrise and sunset. Today, Cape Jason also hosts various concerts and kite festivals.

3. Method

3.1. Purpose and Importance of Research

This study is based on the assumption that visitor reviews play a critical role in the development of destinations and in directing demand for destinations (Erdoğan & Yaşarsoy, 2023; Gedik, 2021). The main purpose of the research is to analyze the visitor

experiences of Cape Jason and the Church, which are important tourist attractions in the Perşembe district of Ordu province. In addition, this study aims to develop specific recommendations based on the research findings to increase awareness of Cape Jason and the Church and to ensure the proper management of the tourist attraction. The primary motivation for selecting this tourist attraction for the study was its status as one of the most visited tourist attractions in the region and the limited scientific research available on the area. Therefore, it is believed that this study on Cape Jason and the Church will contribute to tourism literature in general and destination management decisions regarding tourist attractions in particular.

3.2. Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative research design, as it enables an in-depth understanding of subjective meanings and experience-based interpretations (Creswell & Creswell, 2017; Patton, 2014). Within this framework, the netnography approach was employed to analyze user-generated content in online environments. The discipline of netnography was first used by researcher Kozinets to better understand today's individuals, who are increasingly socializing in online communities, from a consumer perspective (Kozinets, 1998). Kozinets is also the scientist who first approached netnography as a discipline, specifically designed to study online cultures and communities, and who sought to highlight the ethical and procedural aspects of the method (Kozinets, 2010). The primary reason for choosing a netnography design was to capture the cultural implications of the findings that emerge from individuals instantly sharing their true feelings, thoughts, and experiences in a digital environment. Furthermore, the netnography design was chosen by researchers due to its cost-effectiveness, eliminating time and space constraints and enabling easy and rapid access to data through online environments.

The population of the study consists of all comments made about Cape Jason and the Church on online platforms, while the sample consists of 201 user comments about Cape Jason and the Church on the TripAdvisor platform. The selection of TripAdvisor as the primary data source is based on its structured review system, global recognition, and its widespread use in tourism research. TripAdvisor allows users to produce more comprehensive, experience-based narratives that include contextual information, personal reflections, and evaluative judgments. This characteristic makes TripAdvisor particularly suitable for qualitative approaches such as netnography, where the depth and richness of user-generated content are essential. In addition, TripAdvisor reviews are organized around specific attractions and are subject to a standardized rating and commenting structure, which enhances the consistency and comparability of the data. Therefore, TripAdvisor was preferred as a more appropriate platform for capturing detailed experiential expressions of tourists.

The sample includes 201 user reviews, which may seem numerically limited; however, in qualitative research, adequacy is determined by data richness and relevance rather than size. In this context, the concept of "information power" suggests that the more information a sample holds that is relevant to the study, the fewer observations are required (Malterud et al., 2016). Accordingly, sample size in qualitative studies depends on several factors, including the specificity of the research aim, the depth and

quality of the data, the use of established theoretical frameworks, and the analytical strategy employed. In the present study, the dataset covers a broad temporal range (2014–2024) and includes diverse experiential expressions, enabling the identification of recurring patterns and meaningful themes. The generation of a large number of codes and thematic structures further indicates that the data provide sufficient depth for interpretative analysis. Therefore, the adequacy of the sample should be evaluated in terms of its information power and analytical richness rather than its numerical size, in line with established qualitative research principles.

3.3. Data Collection Source and Data Collection Tool

To focus on online representations of tourist experiences, content shared by users on the TripAdvisor platform regarding Cape Jason and the Church was used as research data. The document analysis method was applied to systematically analyze the text-based data in question. Document analysis, like other analytical methods in qualitative research, is the systematic examination of the content of printed and electronic materials. The purpose of analyzing and interpreting data is to develop empirical knowledge on the topic under investigation (Bowen, 2009; Corbin & Strauss, 2008).

3.4. Data Collection Process

The first search conducted on the TripAdvisor platform in June 2024 identified a total of 203 comments related to Cape Jason and the Church. Of these reviews, 186 were in Turkish, 8 in English, 3 in German, 1 in Russian, 1 in Italian, 1 in French, 1 in Spanish, 1 in Japanese, and 1 in Arabic. The first comment was made on February 18, 2014, and the last comment was made on June 2, 2024. The comments were then transferred to Microsoft Office Word and examined in detail by researchers. During this process, spelling and grammar errors were corrected, and 2 comments unrelated to the subject and tourist attraction were filtered out. The reviews included in the dataset were written in multiple languages and were translated into English prior to analysis. The translation process was conducted using a two-step approach to ensure accuracy and consistency. First, all non-English comments were translated into English using a professional online translation tool. In the second step, the translated texts were carefully reviewed and checked by the researchers to ensure semantic accuracy, contextual consistency, and the preservation of meaning. Particular attention was paid to culturally specific expressions and tou-

rism-related terminology to avoid misinterpretation. This process was implemented to enhance the reliability and validity of the translated data used in the analysis. Thus, a 22-page raw data document was

created, and the analysis phase was initiated. The research process diagram in Figure 1 was created to provide a clearer understanding of the research process.

Figure 1. Research Process

As can be seen in Figure 1, first, an online platform was selected where comments related to Cape Jason and the Church could be accessed. In the second stage, keywords expressing tourist attraction were determined from the comments on this platform. In the third step, a search was conducted, and 203 comments were accessed. In the next stage, irrelevant comments were removed from this set. In the final stage, a total of 201 comments were included in the analysis for the study.

3.5. Data Analysis

The data obtained from the TripAdvisor platform was analyzed using content analysis. Content analysis is basically the process of classifying data of similar nature around specific concepts and themes using definitions and theories from the literature and organizing and interpreting them in a way that readers can easily understand. In content analysis, qualitative data are systematically organized through a stepwise process in which meaning units are identified and coded, codes are grouped into themes, and these themes are further developed into categories and interpreted in line with the research objectives. This process is consistent with the principles of systematic text condensation, which involves moving from an overall understanding of the data to coding, condensation, and synthesis of meanings (Malterud, 2012). As a result of the content analysis, 802 codes were created, and these 802 codes were grouped under 6 main themes and 53 subthemes, considering the relationships between them. Some comments contained statements that could be associated with more than one theme. These statements were coded under the theme they

fell under. Therefore, some comments were coded in parts under more than one theme. Direct quotations from visitor comments supporting these themes were included. In the study, which was conducted using manual coding, the "MAXQDA 20" qualitative data analysis program was used to create a word cloud. Later, inferences and evaluations were made about this main theme, sub-theme and word cloud.

3.6. Validity and Reliability

To ensure the trustworthiness of the study, the criteria proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985) credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability were systematically addressed. Credibility was enhanced through prolonged engagement with the data and the use of direct quotations from user reviews to support the identified themes, allowing a clear link between raw data and interpretations. Transferability was ensured by providing a detailed description of the research context, data source, and analytical procedures, enabling readers to assess the applicability of the findings to similar contexts. Dependability was achieved by systematically documenting each stage of the research process, including data collection, coding, and theme development, and by repeatedly reviewing the data to ensure consistency across codes and themes. Confirmability was strengthened by maintaining researcher neutrality, grounding interpretations in the data, and conducting an external audit by an expert researcher who evaluated the consistency between the data, codes, and findings. In addition, the raw data are available for review upon request, further supporting the transparency and reliability of the study.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted in accordance with ethical principles. All data used in the study was obtained from TripAdvisor, an open-access and public platform. Therefore, the study does not constitute any ethical violations.

4. Findings

Before presenting the findings regarding the comments evaluated within the scope of the research, Table 1 presents the distribution of the number of stars participants gave to their comments regarding tourist attractions.

Table 1. Distribution of Reviews by Star Rating

Evaluation Score	Number of Comments	Percentage (%)
5 (Excellent)	111	55,2
4 (Very Good)	59	29,4
3 (Medium)	22	10,9
2 (Bad)	7	3,5
1 (Terrible)	2	1,0
Total	201	100

As seen in Table 1, approximately 85% of the reviews were rated for or five stars, which could be considered positive. The proportion of 1- and 2-star reviews (4.5%), which could be considered negative, was quite low. Based on this, it can be said that most visitors were pleased with their visit to Cape Jason and the Church and developed positive feelings about

the destination. Figure 2 presents the monthly distribution of comments related to Cape Jason and the Church. This distribution provides insight into the temporal patterns of visitor engagement and highlights the months during which the tourist attraction receives heightened attention.

Figure 2. Distribution of Comments by Months

Figure 2 indicates that visitor reviews are most concentrated in August. If it is assumed that visitors typically post reviews on the TripAdvisor platform shortly after their visit, this pattern suggests that August represents the peak period of interest in the tourist attraction. After presenting information on the quantitative characteristics of the comments regarding Cape Jason and the Church, main themes and su-

bthemes were generated to draw descriptive inferences about the content of the comments. Table 2 presents the prominent themes and the number of comments related to these themes. Since more than one theme may appear in a single comment, the total number of themes is not equal to the total number of comments.

Table 2. Subthemes and Sample Comments within the Main Theme of Positive Comments

Main Theme	Subtheme
Positive Comments (466)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landscape/Nature (116) <p><i>"...A truly indescribable place with its perfect nature and scenery..."</i></p> <p><i>"...The sea view takes you on a completely different emotional journey..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourist Superstructure (51) <p><i>"...There are seaside tea gardens very close by..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recreational Activities (50) <p><i>"...If you brought a kite with you, you can enjoy flying it..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical and Natural Surroundings (48) <p><i>"...A beautiful historical monument in a pleasant environment and natural surroundings..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calmness/Peace (32) <p><i>"...A place to visit for silence, tranquility, and peace..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Worth Seeing (31) <p><i>"...Cape Jason is a place worth seeing..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Location (25) <p><i>"...The location is magnificent, at the intersection of the land and sea..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transportation (25) <p><i>"...There is transportation here in the morning and evening..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourist Infrastructure (21) <p><i>"...Benches and picnic areas available..."</i></p> <p><i>"...There were signs with explanations in many languages, including Turkish, English, German, Russian and Arabic..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protected/Maintained (18) <p><i>"...One of several well-preserved old churches ..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mythological Story/Legend (15) <p><i>"...Cape Jason has even been the subject of mythologies, the legend of the golden fleece started here..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clean Air/Oxygen (7) <p><i>"...This place has a very different, very clean air..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pristine Environment (5) <p><i>"...The surroundings have been left simple and the natural structure has been preserved..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Security (4) <p><i>"...Protected by security guards and cameras ..."</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction of Tourist Facilities (3) <p><i>"...There are currently tourism facility construction works here..."</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mystical Atmosphere (3) <p><i>"...The church has a mystical earthy scent ..."</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No Crowding (1) <p><i>"...Not being crowded is also an advantage..."</i></p>	

Among the themes that emerge in the content of the comments, it is observed that the frequency of comments that can be classified as "positive comments" is much higher. A total of 18 subthemes emerged under the heading "positive comments" and statements related to these themes were repeated 466 times. Within the main theme of "positive comments", the landscape/nature sub-theme

stands out as the most frequently repeated theme (n=116). The subthemes that stood out within the scope of positive comments were touristic infrastructure (n=51), recreational activities (n=50) and historical buildings/areas (n=48). Table 3 presents subthemes and sample comments under the theme of informing, which is another main theme that emerged intensely in the comments.

Table 3. Subthemes and Sample Comments within the Main Theme of Information

Main Theme	Subtheme
Information (116)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Location/Directions (71) <p><i>"...It is a church located on the seaside at Cape Jason, on the Çaytepe side of Ordu Thursday..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> History of the Church (15) <p><i>"...The church, whose history dates back to the 1800s, is known to have been built by the Greeks..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Architecture of the Church (13) <p><i>"...The interior and exterior of the church reflect classical Orthodox architecture..."</i></p> <p><i>"...The building was built with a masonry construction system and cut stone and rubble stone were used as materials. It is rectangular in shape."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrance Fee (8) <p><i>"...You do not pay any fee to enter the church ..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Name Jason (3) <p><i>"...You can find the name Jason in ancient Greek texts as "Iason"..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of the Land (2) <p><i>"...The region has been declared a first degree protected area..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Closed Days (2) <p><i>"...It was closed on Mondays, and there was no one there when we went..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Original State of the Church (2) <p><i>"...The main part of the church has been destroyed. A new one was built in its place later..."</i></p>

Another frequently recurring theme in the comments was the main theme of information (n=116). Within this scope, it was observed that the sub-theme related to location/route information (n=71) was the most frequently recurring. Subthemes such as the history of the church, the architecture of the

church, and the entrance fee are other subthemes that emerged within the main theme of information. Table 4 presents the subthemes and sample comments that emerged within the main theme of negative comments.

Table 4. Subthemes and Sample Comments under the Main Theme of Negative Comments

Main Theme	Subtheme
Negative Comments (97)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Church is Closed (24) <p><i>"...We couldn't visit the inside of the church because it was closed..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient Tourist Infrastructure (14) <p><i>"...It's like there's no lighting inside..."</i></p> <p><i>"...Explanations are too few and insufficient ..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wind (11) <p><i>"...It is a very windy place and you may get a headache from the wind ..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of maintenance (11) <p><i>"...Unfortunately, the church and its surroundings are very neglected..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste of Time (7) <p><i>"...Not worth your time..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Pollution (4) <p><i>"...Those who come to such beautiful places leave a piece of themselves, unfortunately I don't know why..."</i></p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visual Pollution (3) <p><i>"...The writings on the church walls create an ugly image..."</i></p>

Negative Comments (97)

- Indifference of Local Governments (3)
"...The municipality is indifferent..."

- Far from the Center/City (3)
"...A little far from the center..."

- Road Conditions (3)
"...The roads are quite winding..."

- Lack of Service Quality (3)
"...There are cafe-like businesses very close by, but their menus are very inadequate..."

- Sea (2)
"...The sea is not very suitable for swimming..."

- Not Receiving Enough Attention (2)
"...The region is a spot that has not received enough attention for some reason since its participation in tourism..."

- Restoration (2)
"...It is also interesting that they put electrical outlets in the restored historic church..."

- Crowd (2)
"...It gets too crowded..."

- Lack of Promotion (2)
"...Unfortunately, it has not been promoted sufficiently from a touristic perspective..."

- High Price (1)
"...There are cafes but expensive..."

Seventeen different subthemes emerged within the main theme of negative comments. From these comments, it is possible to understand the factors that create negativity regarding tourist attraction. The most frequently occurring subthemes were the church being closed (n=24), inadequate tourist in-

frastructure (n=14), wind (n=11), and lack of maintenance (n=11). Table 5 presents subthemes, which are less frequently repeated main themes within the recommendations, warnings, and other subthemes that do not fit into any category.

Table 4. Subthemes and Sample Comments under the Main Theme of Negative Comments

Main Theme	Subtheme
Recommendations (69)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sunrise/Sunset (37) <i>"...The best place to watch the sunset is recommended ..."</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gastronomic Product Experience (15) <i>"...Eat hazelnut dessert at the cafe right next to the church, you won't regret it..."</i> <i>"...Have a drink with Ordu toast..."</i> <i>"...In mid-August, you can buy figs and fresh hazelnuts from locals who gather and sell black figs from trees..."</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate dressing recommendations (6) <i>"...I recommend comfortable clothes and comfortable shoes..."</i> <i>"...It's a bit windy, so you might want to bring a light jacket for the kids..."</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reason for visit (5) <i>"...If you love nature and scenery, I definitely recommend stopping by..."</i> <i>"...I especially recommend it to history buffs..."</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel Time (4) <i>"...The Cape Jason Church and Lighthouse were all very beautiful with wildflowers in the spring months..."</i> <i>"...If possible, don't go on weekends as it gets very crowded..."</i>

Warnings (4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Governments (2) <i>"...The area surrounding the Church of Jason should be better organized and beautified..."</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourism/Environmental Awareness (2) <i>"...Lets not litter the environment. Let's preserve our history..."</i>
Other (50)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jason/Lighthouse (42) <i>"...When you walk toward the lighthouse at the tip, you experience an indescribable sense of peace in the sound of the powerful waves of the sea..."</i> Natural Studio (7) <i>"...Hosting wedding photos..."</i> Sea Water (1) <i>"...The sea water was very clean..."</i>

The most frequently recurring subthemes within the main theme of "recommendations" are "sunrise/sunset" and "gastronomic product experience." Comments emphasize that Cape Jason is an excellent spot for watching sunrise or sunset. Visitors have also offered suggestions for their favorite gastronomic experiences. Products such as hazelnut dessert, Ordu Toast, black figs, fresh hazelnuts, gözleme, and ayran are among the recommended items. In addition, although less frequently repeated, subthemes covering different suggestions such as "travel time," "appropriate dress" and "reason for visit" are mentioned in the comments. The subthemes under the main theme of 'warning' are "warnings to local authorities" and "tourism/environmental awareness". These themes are repeated in only a few comments. Among the subthemes in the "Other" category, the subtheme consisting of comments mentioning the

lighthouse on Cape Jason is particularly frequently repeated.

Although the findings are presented under descriptive categories such as positive comments, negative comments, information, and recommendations, a deeper examination of the subthemes reveals underlying conceptual patterns. These categories should not be interpreted merely as surface-level classifications; rather, they reflect deeper experiential dimensions consistent with the memorable tourism experience (MTE) framework. Based on this perspective, the findings can be reinterpreted under three overarching experiential dimensions. To further clarify the relationship between the identified themes and the underlying experiential dimensions, the thematic structure is systematically mapped onto the components of memorable tourism experience (MTE), as presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Mapping of Identified Themes with MTE Dimensions

Main Theme	Subthemes (Examples)	MTE Dimension	Conceptual Interpretation
Positive Comments	Landscape/Nature, Calmness, Scenic view, Clean air, Mystical atmosphere	Hedonic (Emotional)	Visitors experience pleasure, relaxation, and aesthetic appreciation
	Historical surroundings, Mythological stories	Cognitive (Knowledge)	Visitors seek meaning and cultural understanding
	Recreational activities, accessibility	Behavioral (Engagement)	Active participation and interaction with destination
Information	Location, history, architecture, entrance fee	Cognitive (Knowledge)	Information-seeking and interpretation-oriented experience
Negative Comments	Lack of maintenance, infrastructure problems, closed church	Experiential Disruption	Factors that weaken or interrupt memorability of experience
	Accessibility, distance, poor service	Behavioral Constraint	Barriers limiting full experience engagement
Recommendations	Sunrise/sunset, gastronomy	Behavioral (Post-experience engagement)	Visitors extend experience through sharing and suggesting
	Travel advice, clothing suggestions	Behavioral (eWOM)	Knowledge transfer to future visitors

5. Conclusion

This study analyzed the visitor experiences at Cape Jason and the Church. In this context, 201 reviews posted on TripAdvisor about Cape Jason and the Church was examined. Most of the reviews (approximately 93%) were written in Turkish. Based on this, it can be said that Cape Jason and the Church cater primarily to domestic tourism demand and that visitors to this site are mostly local tourists. Additionally, the comments indicate that a substantial majority of visitors (approximately 85%) expressed satisfaction with their experience at the tourist attraction.

A content analysis was conducted on 201 online reviews obtained from TripAdvisor regarding the Cape Jason and the Church. As a result of the content analysis, 802 codes were created, and the relationships between the 802 codes were carefully examined and grouped under 6 main themes and 53 subthemes. These main themes consist of positive reviews, negative reviews, recommendations, information, warnings, and other themes. Eighteen subthemes were identified for positive comments, 17 subthemes for negative comments, 6 subthemes for the main theme of "Recommendation," 8 subthemes under the main theme of "Information," 2 subthemes under the main theme of "Warning," and 3 subthemes under the "Other" theme.

From the online reviews examined about Cape Jason and the Church, it is clear that its tourist appeal plays an important role in visitors gaining a largely positive impression of the place. In particular, the strong emphasis on natural beauty, scenery, and environmental aesthetics reveals that visitors perceive this area not only as a tourist attraction but also as a place for emotional and visual experiences. These findings highlight that nature-based destinations with strong visual appeal play a central role in shaping visitor preferences. These observations are well aligned with the findings of Breiby (2015), whose research identifies "scenery/viewing", "harmony", and "genuineness" as central aesthetic dimensions in nature-based tourism and demonstrates that these dimensions significantly influence tourist satisfaction, positive emotions, and loyalty. Likewise, studies by Wen et al. (2024) in Zhangjiajie National Forest Park and by Adigüzel and Batman (2024) in recreational landscapes confirm that perceived visual quality and aesthetic experiential qualities critically affect visitor satisfaction and destination choice, supporting the findings of the present study. These findings go beyond a descriptive identification of themes by demonstrating how different dimensions of visitor experience interact and collectively shape overall satisfaction and perception. In this sense, the study provides a more integrated and interpretive understanding of tourist experiences in heritage-based destinations. Therefore, the study contributes to the literature not only by identifying visitor experience themes but also by theoretically reinterpreting

these themes within the multidimensional structure of memorable tourism experiences.

However, the need for guidance and content that stands out under the theme of "information" shows that visitors do not want to settle for just a spatial experience but also want to access historical and cultural contexts. This situation suggests that visitors are not passive consumers, but rather more conscious tourists who value information, narrative, and context. Although negative comments are fewer in number, their concentration on certain themes indicates that while the overall satisfaction level with tourist attractions is high, some fundamental issues are still perceived as significant. In particular, the fact that issues such as the church being closed which could be resolved with simple interventions can negatively impact on the visitor experience highlights how managerial shortcomings can lead to potential missed opportunities.

6. Discussion

This section aims to interpret the findings of the study in relation to the existing literature and to position the results within a broader theoretical context. The emergence of visitors' recommendations as a main theme indicates that a sense of ownership towards the region has developed and that they are highly motivated to share their experiences with others. In particular, the prominence of local food products, especially in these suggestions, indicates that gastronomic identity has a strong potential to become a touristic product. These findings also point to the multidimensional nature of visitor experiences, which can be further interpreted within a theoretical framework.

The findings of this study can also be interpreted within the framework of memorable tourism experience (MTE) (Kim et al., 2012). Although the themes identified in this study are based on the categorization of online reviews, they reflect underlying experiential dimensions discussed in the MTE literature. In particular, the strong emphasis on landscape, nature and visual aesthetics in positive comments corresponds to the hedonic and refreshment dimensions of memorable experiences, as these elements contribute to pleasure, relaxation, and emotional engagement. The frequently expressed need for information regarding the historical and cultural context of the site indicates the presence of a cognitive (knowledge-based) dimension of experience. In addition, visitor recommendations and suggestions reflect post-experience involvement and behavioral intentions, suggesting that the experience extends beyond the visit itself. On the other hand, negative comments related to infrastructure and maintenance can be interpreted as factors that weaken the memorability of the experience by creating dissatisfaction or expectation mismatch. Taken together, these

findings suggest that the visitor experiences in Cape Jason and the Church are not limited to simple evaluations, but are shaped by multiple experiential dimensions consistent with the MTE framework.

When we look at the studies examining visitor experiences in the literature, the study conducted by Kaya & Kaya (2023) examining the opinions of the visitors who experienced Uzungöl, positive findings such as ambiance/view, natural beauty, worth seeing, clean air, recreational opportunities, food and beverage and accommodation opportunities, and negative findings such as pollution, crowding, high prices, poor quality service and distance, which is similar to the findings of this study. Scalabrini et al. (2023) analyzed the opinions of tourists visiting Montesinho Nature Park (Portugal), Douro International Nature Park (Portugal), and Arribes del Duero Nature Park (Spain) based on TripAdvisor reviews. For Montesinho, two dimensions (landscape and nature), for Douro International, two dimensions (activities and nature), and for Arribes del Duero, three dimensions (water-based activities, nature, and activities) were identified, with the common dimension across all three natural parks being nature. The findings regarding landscape/nature and activities for Cape Jason and the Church suggest that similar results were obtained in this study. The study conducted by Erşahin & Şahbaz (2024), which examined visitor comments about Gülhane Park, showed positive results such as transportation and accessibility, quiet and peaceful, recreational opportunities, clean, well-maintained, and orderly, which are in line with the findings of this study. Saoualih et al. (2024) evaluated the experiences of tourists visiting the Majorelle Garden in Marrakech, Morocco, through TripAdvisor platform reviews. In this context, the findings that visitors mostly had positive feelings and positive experiences related to natural beauty, photographic appeal, and souvenir shopping, while negative experiences were related to a garden with nothing extraordinary and excessive crowds, are consistent with the findings of this study. Similarly, Altınay Özdemir & Topaloğlu (2023) determined that the themes of scenery and positive comments stood out in online comments about the ancient city of Knidos. In a study conducted by Kara & Çeken (2025) examining the opinions of tourists visiting Ulugöl Nature Park, it was determined that the vast majority of visitors (89%) were satisfied with the tourist attraction and that the most common positive comments focused on natural wonders/landscapes. The high overall satisfaction levels of tourists who shared reviews about Cape Jason and the Church, and the fact that positive reviews mostly emphasize the scenery/nature, indicate similar results. Güven, Mazlum & Şahin (2025) examined 569 online reviews on the TripAdvisor platform regarding natural areas in the province of Balıkesir and found that negative reviews mentioned overcrowding, environmental

pollution, neglect, and expectations that were not met. The findings of this study are similar to the negative findings regarding Cape Jason and the Church.

7. Theoretical Implications

From a theoretical perspective, this study suggests that destination management strategies should be explicitly designed in accordance with the experience-based tourism framework and electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) theory. The experience-based approach implies that destinations should move beyond the provision of physical attractions and instead focus on the deliberate design of emotional, cognitive, and sensory experiences. Accordingly, destination managers are encouraged to structure tourism products and services in ways that facilitate meaning-making, emotional engagement, and memorable experiences, as these elements are central determinants of satisfaction and loyalty. In this respect, the study contributes to the literature by demonstrating how online user-generated content can be used not only to identify themes but also to interpret the multidimensional structure of tourist experiences.

In line with eWOM theory, the findings indicate that visitors' online narratives function not only as reflections of individual experiences but also as strategic communication tools that shape destination image and influence potential visitors' decision-making processes. Therefore, destination managers should actively monitor, interpret, and respond to online reviews, integrating visitor feedback into continuous service improvement and communication strategies. From a theoretical perspective, managing online reviews should be regarded as an integral component of experience design and destination governance rather than as a post-visit marketing activity.

8. Practical Implications

Cape Jason offers a multidimensional visitor experience not only with its natural beauty but also with its historical texture and local elements. Managing this experience in a sustainable and effective manner is possible with the cooperation and efforts of local administrations and stakeholders. In this context, it is important for stakeholders with initiatives regarding Cape Jason and the Church to understand visitors' expectations and the elements that stand out in their experiences. The research provides local stakeholders with an important source of information by drawing conclusions from TripAdvisor reviews related to tourist appeal.

In addition to these findings, several practical implications can be derived for destination management. The strong emphasis on landscape and natural be-

auty indicates that Cape Jason should not only be preserved but also designed as an experiential space that enhances visitors' emotional engagement through elements such as observation areas, walking paths, and quiet resting zones. At the same time, the prominent need for information suggests that visitors seek not only to observe but also to understand the historical and cultural context of the destination; therefore, digital guides, interpretive panels, and multilingual storytelling tools should be developed to enrich the visitor experience. Furthermore, although negative comments are relatively limited, they highlight manageable issues such as infrastructure deficiencies, maintenance problems, and accessibility constraints, indicating that relatively small managerial interventions could lead to substantial improvements in visitor satisfaction. In addition, the frequent references to local gastronomic products suggest that these elements should be more strategically integrated into destination branding and experience design. Finally, concerns related to environmental awareness and local governance underline the importance of incorporating sustainability-oriented practices into both management strategies and communication processes. Despite these theoretical and practical contributions, the study is subject to several limitations.

9. Limitations

This study has several limitations. The first and most important is that the study data was obtained from the TripAdvisor platform and is based solely on user reviews. In this context, the research findings could be expanded by analyzing user reviews on platforms such as Google Maps, Lonely Planet, etc. Second, there is the issue of representativeness of the study findings with social media data. Therefore, social media data should be approached with caution and combined with other types of data, such as interviews, observations, and surveys. Third, social media data may inherently be biased toward specific users and locations. Users, motivated by their cultural practices and values, may express overly positive or negative opinions about destinations, which can be reflected in social media content, leading potential tourists to develop biases toward the destination. Fourth, the data collected is from a specific time period. Due to the ever-changing and dynamic nature of digital applications and online environments, it is assumed that the results of future research conducted using comments on the same platform may differ. Furthermore, this study is relatively cross-sectional. The online participation of stakeholders from whom data was obtained takes place in a dynamic environment, and therefore longitudinal studies should be conducted to clarify our understanding of the long-term evolution of opinions (Xiang & Gretzel, 2010).

10. Future Research

In line with the limitations of this study, future research could adopt a comparative approach by examining visitor experiences across different destinations and cultural contexts. In particular, analyzing similar heritage sites or nature-based destinations would contribute to a deeper understanding of how experiential patterns vary depending on contextual factors. We recommend that future research be conducted to comparatively examine the motivations, expectations, and satisfaction levels of tourists visiting tourist attractions, as well as to explore how these factors interact with different dimensions of memorable tourism experience (MTE), such as hedonism, novelty, involvement, and knowledge. Since MTE is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct that shapes how tourism experiences are remembered and evaluated over time, examining these dimensions across different visitor segments and cultural contexts would provide deeper insights into the formation of memorable experiences and their influence on behavioral intentions.

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